

CHEMICAL EXAMINATION OF CLERODENDRON INFORTUNATUM. PART I.

BY HIRENDRA NATH BANERJEE.

Clerodendron infortunatum or the India *Bhant* or *Bhat* (N. O. *Verbenaceæ*) is a gregarious shrub, very common in the warm regions throughout India from Gurhwal and Assam to Ceylon. The importance of the plant from medicinal point of view has been advocated by Rheede, Dr. Bhola Nath Bose (*Pharmacopœia of India*) and Thornton (*Pharmacographica Indica*, V., p. 79) as vermifuge, anthelmintic and also as a cheap and efficient substitute for *Chiretta*. In the indigenous system the young twigs of *Bhant* are ground into a thick paste and the pills prepared therefrom swallowed with water, for the destruction of intestinal worms.

In view of the facts mentioned above a systematic chemical investigation was undertaken to find out the active principles responsible for the therapeutic action of the drug and also as far as possible to elucidate their chemical constitution.

E X P E R I M E N T A L .

Test for Alkaloids.—50 G. of air-dried, finely powdered leaves when treated with Prollius fluid did not indicate the presence of any alkaloid.

TABLE I.

Analysis of leaf.

Ash	8.04%
Protein	...	27.12 (N, 3.33)	
Crude fibre	...	14.84	
Free reducing sugars	...	3.00	
Total sugars after inversion	...	17.05	

TABLE II.

Analysis of Leaf-ash.

Ash soluble in water	...	45.08%
Ash soluble in acid	...	47.57
Insolubles	...	7.35
SiO ₂	...	7.35
MnO ₂	...	0.116
Fe ₂ O ₃	...	2.45
P ₂ O ₅	...	2.82
CaO	...	24.70
MgO	...	10.28
Total alkali [Na ₂ O + K ₂ O]	...	32.28
Cl	...	2.20
SO ₃	...	8.84
CO ₂	...	8.40
Total determined	...	99.76%

Extraction with Various Solvents.—In order to ascertain the general character of the constituents present, 193 g. of air-dried leaf-powder were extracted successively in a Soxhlet apparatus with various solvents. The different extracts, thus obtained, were dried at 100° and weighed.

TABLE III.

Petroleum ether (b. p. 30-50°) extract	3.85%
Ether extract	2.31
Chloroform extract	1.82
Absolute alcohol	8.75
Water extract	14.10
Residue left over	69.00
Loss by diff.	—
					100

Petroleum Ether Extract. Isolation of Clerodin.

The extract obtained from 3 kg. of air-dried leaf-powder consisted of a deep greenish yellow solution with an extremely bitter taste. On concentration, crystals appeared. These on recrystallisation from boiling 50% aqueous alcohol (charcoal) were obtained as colourless long glistening needles, extremely bitter in taste, m. p. 161°-62°.

The petroleum ether mother liquor was distilled off to remove the last traces of petroleum, when a deep green pasty mass was obtained. It was distilled in steam and the distillate was found to be turbid but free from any bitter taste. This distillate was found to contain a volatile essential oil with a strong odour of the drug. By repeated extraction with 60% alcohol a further crop of the bitter substance was obtained from the pasty mass. The total yield of the bitter substance amounted to 0.12% of the air-dried leaf.

Interesting physiological and chemical properties of the bitter substance, on which a note has been published (*Science and Culture*, 1936, 2, 163), will be the subject of a future communication. The substance has been named *clerodin*.

After complete removal of clerodin, the pasty mass was repeatedly extracted with 80% alcohol. The extract gave large silvery plates which after recrystallisation from 80% alcohol (charcoal) appeared as hexagonal plates, m. p. 147°-48° answering to all the colour reactions of *sterols*, and getting precipitated by alcoholic digitonin. The *acetyl* derivative melted at 127°-28°. The yield of sterol was less than 0.01% of the Bhand leaf. After

separation of the sterol the mother liquor deposits a substance in flakes in extremely small quantity, which seemed to be an alcohol, m. p. 75°.

The dark pasty residue was dissolved in ether and purified (charcoal and Fieser's earth). After removal of the solvent a dark-coloured butter-like mass was obtained. 12 G. of this substance were saponified and the crude fatty acids liberated and removed. The aqueous portion after treatment with barium carbonate and filtration was concentrated to a syrup under reduced pressure, and identified as glycerol by the acrolein test. The paste, therefore, contains a fixed oil. Determination of iodine value (76.1-75.7) and saponification value (186-176.1) shows that it contained much impurities, which could not be easily removed. 100 G. was, therefore, saponified with alcoholic potash, alcohol removed and the soap dissolved in water, when a rubber-like elastic cake (20 g.) separated out, and was removed. The soap solution was thoroughly washed with ether to remove all unsaponifiable matter, and the free fatty acids liberated and obtained in pure state.

TABLE IV.

Constants of the free fatty acid mixture.

Iodine-value (Hanus).	Neutralisation value.	Mean M. W.	Unsaponifiable matter.
111.42	183.9	305	4.75 %

The fatty acids were then separated into their solid and liquid components by the Twitchell process (*J. Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1921, 13, 806).

TABLE V.

	Yield	Iodine value.	Ref. index.	Neutralisation value.	Mean M. W.
Liquid acid ...	80 %	138.1	1.4840 at 30°	196	285.7
Solid acid ...	20	6.79	m. p. 70° s. p. 60°	170	329.4

Determination of the Individual Liquid Fatty Acids.—The liquid acid mixture obtained above was brominated at -10° in dry ether solution according to Eibner and Muggenthaler (Lewkowitsch, "Chemical Technology and Analysis of Oils, Fats, Waxes," Vol. I, p. 585).

Linolenic Acid.—After bromination, ether-insoluble hexabromide was precipitated, which was filtered, washed free from bromine, thoroughly dried and weighed. After recrystallisation from benzene the bromide melted at 177° - 78° . (Found: Br, 63.66. Calc. for $C_{18}H_{30}O_2Br_6$: Br, 63.33 per cent).

The mother liquor from the ether-insoluble hexabromide was washed thoroughly with hypo and then with water. The ether was then distilled off and the residue redissolved in boiling petroleum ether and on cooling linolic tetrabromide did not separate.

Oleic Acid.—The petroleum ether solution was then evaporated when a brown oily mass consisting entirely of oleic dibromide was obtained. (Found: Br, 36.08. Calc. for $C_{18}H_{34}O_2Br_2$: Br, 36.18 per cent).

TABLE VI.

Composition of the liquid acid mixture.

	Yield.	Corresponding acid calculated.	Percentage of each acid in the mixture.
Oleic dibromide	2.50	1.60	74.88% Oleic
Linolenic hexabromide	1.47	0.54	25.13% Linolenic

Examination of the Solid Acids.—The solid acid mixture (15 g.) was converted into the methyl ester and fractionally distilled under reduced pressure (1 mm.). The saponification values of the different fractions were determined from which the mean M. W. were calculated. The respective acids were then liberated from their different fractions and their melting points determined.

TABLE VII.

Temp.	Wt.	Saponification value.	Mean M.W.	M. p. of liberated acid.	% of each in solid acid.
160—170°	1.62 g.	197.6	283.9	66-67°	
170—175°	2.18	194.8	287.9	66-68°	
175—180°	1.22	192.2	291.9	67-68°	Stearic acid% 48.82
180—190° rising up to					
200°	4.83	174.0	321.9	75-77°	Lignoceric acid

Residue weighing 2.1 g was found to consist mainly of crude lignoceric acid.

Unsaponifiable Matter.

The unsaponifiable matter which was obtained as a non-crystalline mass with a waxy appearance and deep orange colour was preserved in a vacuum desiccator in a dark place. From this product after complete separation of all sterols, first by freezing out its methyl alcoholic solution, and then by precipitation with digitonin, the two pigments carotin and xanthophyll were separated by the method of Willstätter. These were identified by spectroscopic analysis as well as $SbCl_3$ reaction and Molisch's test.

Sterol.

The sterol portion obtained by freezing out the methyl alcoholic solution of the unsaponifiable matter after repeated crystallisation from alcohol with animal charcoal did not give a definite crystalline product with a sharp melting point. It melted at $138-140^\circ$ with softening at 135° . The acetate prepared direct from this product softens at 65° and melts at $68-70^\circ$. The whole of the sterol was, therefore, precipitated from solution by digitonin and the digitonide converted direct into the acetate. The sterol acetate, thus obtained, was a tuft of needles, m.p. $125-27^\circ$. The total amount of the sterol was, therefore, quantitatively estimated by the digitonin method of Windaus and the amount was found to be 1.20% of the oil.

The mother liquor left after separation of the sterol as digitonide was freed from any excess of digitonin and a quantity of waxy material with a characteristic odour was obtained. This dissolved completely in boiling acetic anhydride from which nothing separates on cooling. This evidently indicates that naturally occurring hydrocarbons are not present in any appreciable quantity but that aliphatic alcohols probably constitute the rest of the unsaponifiable matter.

The Ether Extract.—The ether extract of the leaf-powder after purification gave an oil which was found to be similar in composition to the oil obtained from the leaf by extraction with light petroleum ether. Saponification value, 184; iodine value, 76.23.

The viscous mass was found to contain traces of gallic acid, giving blue-black colouration with ferric chloride and a positive Young test for gallic acid (*Chem. News*, 1883, 48, 31).

The Chloroform extract was not bitter and did not give any crystalline product. After extraction with 3% hydrochloric acid, the extract failed to give the usual test for the presence of alkaloids.

The Alcoholic extract on concentration and standing did not give any crystalline substance. After complete removal of the alcohol, the residue was dissolved in water. The opalescent solution, thus obtained, was thoroughly extracted with ether. From the ether solution gallic acid was obtained and identified by the preparation of tri-acetyl derivative, m. p. 168-69°.

The aqueous solution after ether treatment was treated with lead acetate and then with lead subacetate. The filtrate freed from the precipitates was treated with sulphuretted hydrogen and the lead-free solution was concentrated to a syrup. The syrup reduced Fehling's solution and the amount of reduction did not show any increase after boiling with hydrochloric acid. The syrup was laevo-rotatory and the sugar content estimated polarimetrically agreed fairly well with that estimated by Benedict's method and was 6.12% of the total alcoholic extract. Copious crystals of osazone were obtained, m.p. 202°-203°.

The Lead Acetate Precipitate was decomposed in aqueous suspension and the de-lead material was found to consist of tannins only. Similarly the lead subacetate precipitate was found to contain tannin and a reducing sugar.

The Aqueous Extract.—The aqueous extract was thoroughly examined and found to consist of reducing sugars, traces of tannin, proteins, chlorides and sulphates.

TABLE VIII.

Amount of clerodin in different parts of the Bhand plant.

Young leaves & twigs collected before rains	0.12%
„ „ just after rains	0.55%
Old leaves	0.05%
Stem and roots	traces only.

Some Physiological Properties of Clerodin.

Effect of Clerodin on Red Blood Corpuscles.—Weil washed R.B.C. suspended in physiological saline (2 c.c.) was added to 8 c.c. of saturated solution of clerodin (0.06%) in isotonic saline and thoroughly mixed

together. The mixture was incubated at 37° for 24 hours, after which the R.B.C. was found to have completely settled down leaving a clear colourless solution above. Under the microscope the corpuscles were found to be intact showing that clerodin has no hæmolytic action on human R.B.C.

Bactericidal Action on *B. Coli*.—A 12 hours' culture of *B. Coli* in Nutrient broth (1 part) and clerodin solution (1 part) in sterile normal saline were thoroughly mixed and incubated for 24 hours at 37°. A subculture made from this mixture showed that *B. Coli* was not killed. Similar results were observed with different media, e.g., peptone solution, with lactose and glucose. Growth of *B. Coli* was evident by the production of acid and gas. Saturated aqueous solution of clerodin has no bactericidal property as tested against *B. Coli*, the most common member of the intestinal Flora.

Anthelmintic Property: Toxicity to Earthworms.—The toxicity of clerodin to earthworms was investigated according to the method of Sollman (*J. Pharm. and Exp. Therap.*, 1918, 12, 129). The experience of Straub and Tradelenberg and also of Sollman indicates that in some cases the toxicity of drugs to earthworms may run more or less parallel with their toxicity to parasitic worms, although earthworms belong to a totally distinct zoological group. Drugs toxic to earthworms are considered to have possibilities as anthelmintics (Chopra and Chandler "Anthelmintic and their Uses," p. 20). In the present case clerodin has been found to kill earthworms in aqueous solution within 30 minutes.

Small fish *apolocheilus melastigma* were killed by such solution in half an hour and also mosquito larvæ in two hours, when experiments were carried out with them according to Fink and Haller (*J. Econ. Entom.*, 1936, 29, 595). From all these experiments it will be evident that clerodin is toxic to lower order of life.

Clerodin is soluble in hydrochloric acid, olive oil, castor oil, glycerol, and slightly in liquid paraffin and vaselin. To see how far the drug may act injuriously to mammals, 0.1 g. of clerodin dissolved in 10 c.c. of olive oil was fed to a rabbit (body wt., 1.2 kg.). No injurious effect whatever was observed. Clerodin may, therefore, act as a vermifuge without any injurious effect on the host.

My thanks are due to Sir J. C. Bose, Prof. N. C. Nag and Dr. J. P. Sarcar for the interest they have shown and to Prof. J. C. Ghosh for encouragement and advice.